

THE TEACHING PLACE AS AN EPISTEMOLOGICAL FOUNDATION OF PEDAGOGICAL PRACTICE IN THE ICT ERA

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Mônica Nadja Silva d'Almeida Caniçali

Master's student in Education Sciences at the University del Salvador (USAL), Buenos Aires (AR). Specialist in Brazilian Literature from Faculdades Integradas de Jacarepaguá (FIJ, 2005). Graduated in Literature: Portuguese-Spanish from the Faculty of Human Sciences of Aracruz (FACHA, 2003). Professor at the Faculty of Human Sciences of Aracruz (FACHA). Spanish Language Teacher at Wizard Brasil (Aracruz Unit - ES). Works as an Educational Technician with the Special Educational Technology Advisory Team of the State Department of Education of Espírito Santo (SEDU).

Sérgio Rodrigues de Souza

Pedagogue and Philosopher. Scientific Consultant.

ABSTRACT

This work has as its theme 'the teaching place as an epistemological foundation of pedagogical praxis in the ERA TIC' and brings as a problem the difficulty that teachers face in working using information and communication technologies, nowadays because they do not have a methodological tool that gives them adequate support for the development of their didactic-pedagogical activities in the classrooms. The general objective of this work is to propose the elaboration of a guiding principle of methodological activity in which education professionals can explore, as much as possible, the intellectual and cognitive potential of their students through ICT tools. This text is relevant for the educational sciences and for the pedagogical sciences due to the relevance to the development of a new academic mentality of producing teaching and learning, in which new elements are added to the reality of the teacher and the student. As a research methodology, the factual, exploratory, analytical and descriptive bibliographic search was used, considering that through such a method it would be possible to achieve the presented objectives, which was successfully achieved. The main concepts that guide the text are Teaching Place and ICT Era. The proposal with this text is to present a concept for the term Teaching Place, created by the authors of this work in order to provide a scientific, exploratory, pedagogical, didactic and methodological direction for studies involving Information and Communication Technologies. As a branch of science chosen to support our idea, we chose Epistemology as it represents a category of Philosophy that aims to study the origin, structure, methods and validity of knowledge. Society has become more complex every day, given the scientific and epistemological advances that arise, without having an adequate tool for the didactic management of everything that is posted, without any validation. This is

also because individuals and schools do not know how to do such a thing. Therefore, we propose the Teaching Place, as an Epistemological Didactic Space, a facilitator that makes it possible to make the connection between Prhónesis and Episteme. In the ICT Era, every school must assume a formal didactic character, in addition to its students, because it is not enough to have knowledge and know what to do with it or where to apply it, it is necessary to be able to make them generate new scientific knowledge, in a deliberative self-didactic process, in addition to the necessary capacity to share knowledge for the success of any pedagogical enterprise of the 21st century.

Keywords: Teaching Place. It was ICT. Didactics . Methodology .

INTRODUCTION

The investigative fields of the respective human and social sciences are always very rich in possibilities and, at the same time, very lacking in innovations that can truly delimit objective differences capable of promoting relative changes in values in the thoughts and actions of teachers. We dare to explain the terrible paradox to which we have now alluded, because any doubt, when left open, is always a very prone field for the emergence of assumptions, generally the most absurd ones, failing, with such scientific aberrations that are proposed in the eagerness to answer open questions, present nothing relevant to the scientific community, much less to society in general. Science always seeks to respond to the anxieties and questions outlined by the current model of society, which, the more complex it is, the more difficult and embarrassing the questions raised.

The proposal with this essay is to present a concept for the term *teaching place*, an expression that was created through us with the purpose of providing a scientific, exploratory, pedagogical, didactic and methodological direction for studies involving *Information Technologies and Communication*. As the branch of science chosen to support our idea, we chose epistemology, as it represents a category of Philosophy that aims to study the origin, structure, methods and validity of knowledge.

Each era will create and have its concepts with the purpose of maintaining the minimum stability necessary for conducting technical and scientific work, understanding that its existence is a minimum condition for human thought to be able to produce tangible connections between theoretical assumptions and categories existing didactics. Thomas Kuhn (1922-1996) would use the concept of paradigms to explain and expand the understanding of this condition. However, one cannot fail to understand that every paradigm is created and sustained around a term that functions as a directional axis, a guiding thread, to provide the epistemological support of the ideas that may involve future systematic developments. (KHUN, 1978).

Therefore, creating a new term that provides support for investigative, didactic and pedagogical work cannot be a task that must be proposed based on a gap, however, it must first present as a basis a real need that, without this concept, would not have been possible. advance academically with scientific work.

By way of clarification, in the sciences, there is always a need to have a base element through which the gains, advances and directions taken with new investigations can be defined. Dialectical materialism has proven to be the safest method to apply in this investigative preamble, because it allows a greater possibility of understanding and comprehending the internal and external causes of the object under study, followed by other investigation techniques that prove necessary, according to with the nature of the object to be analyzed in depth. What we intend to make transparent is that there will always be a pressing need to know the target object and as many of the elements as possible that, in some way or not, may or may not exert influence, directly and/or indirectly, on it.

The introduction of information and communication technologies into the pedagogical system has generated a broad need for new knowledge, which proves capable of providing equanimity to the teaching and learning processes in classes and, even more so, despite all the possibilities of didactic advances, there is a whole range of well-organized obstacles on the part of teachers and teachers and equally on the part of the educational system of the Brazilian public, because maintaining the archaic format of offering education does not present the slightest need to evolve teaching praxis because, since this evolves there will be no way for it to return to the point of what is conceived and manipulated today.

These advances have caused a lot of fear among actors who carry out their activities as teachers and teachers, because since their initial training they have not been prepared enough to achieve innovation in their practical methods of didactic-methodological work. This causes a phenomenal delay in the teaching and learning processes, because by not questioning the validity and effectiveness of the methods that are being applied in the teaching processes, critical-evolutionary sense is not practiced, thus not providing the need for improvements and /or improvement of methodologies.

For this reason, every act of technical, scientific and philosophical preparation that masters and teachers present in carrying out their respective roles as teachers is a condition that sustains a state of continuous decadence in basic education and once this situation is remedied and the actors (students and teachers) understand, recognize and absorb the *Teaching Place* , such action will provide great progress for the public educational system, given that they are undertaking a new form of education and science, with an autonomous character, which

deepens the search for knowledge outside from the walls of personal existence and, therefore, interested in promoting technological advances whose central element is the individual and systematic desire to always learn.

On the other hand, the State is unable to prepare teachers and teachers for such progress of thought, because it was not created together with the tools that are available for use with an educational purpose, mechanisms that provide an understanding, a new methodological vision of how to do it with greater efficiency and effectiveness. Without this element that we are now proposing, education based on ICT is doomed to imminent failure.

We understand and recognize that all policies focused on and aimed at implementing technology as a form of educational knowledge in the country were accompanied by training for teachers. Perhaps the available training did not achieve the expected result, as it did not consider the sociological and psychological aspects of the object of study. In this case, reflection must consider the quality and relevance of the courses and not their existence . Another factor that can be cited is the lack of training for the use of technologies in undergraduate and teaching courses, thus forcing governments to think about continuous and exhaustive training.

This can be characterized as the biggest problem faced in changing the culture and paradigm in the use of ICT in schools [*especially public ones*], because during the teacher's technical training the possibilities that these tools can provide in the didactic application of theoretical and practical teachings during classes.

THE TEACHING PLACE

The *Teaching Place* is here considered a new term with the interest of providing didactic support to planned scientific studies that aim to support pedagogical practices that are carried out in such a way that they involve the use of communication and information technologies, especially, in basic education environments. This element, *the Teaching Place*, will function as a milestone to be achieved so that the work presents the necessary fluidity in such a way that success happens, meaning by this, the achievement of a successful teaching and learning process , autonomous and continuous.

Therefore, to provide support to actors, it is necessary to use terms that can support thinking that was previously imaginary and inaccessible, however, with advancement and systematic deepening together with scientific production, it becomes concrete and comes to fruition. In this way, allowing didactic-methodological abstraction, leading the student to an autonomous intellectual process that can be understood based on the exposition by JA Valente,

who speaks of reflective abstraction, where this will enable “the projection of what they extracted from a lower level to a higher collective level or the reorganization of this knowledge in terms of prior knowledge (abstraction on the students’ own ideas)” (VALENTE, 2005, p. 53).

All knowledge, in order to be properly managed, so that it becomes accessible to the greatest possible number of people, thus improving their working conditions, learning and evolutionary processes, requires instruments that enable its interpretation in a way that is autonomous and useful, considering that it enables a broad understanding and production of syntheses.

ICT and the entire apparatus of knowledge and knowledge acquired, elaborated and provided since its emergence have proven to be useless to the State and education due to the lack of a tool that allows the conduction of work, its empirical inference in the field of didactics and bringing students closer to new theories, reaching the conclusion that a technique can only be converted into a useful work tool from the moment one can manage it and apply creativity, imagination and knowledge to it, that is, applying all intellectual capacity to it, in the expectation that new knowledge and new instruments, new products will be produced. In this sense, Valente (2005, p. 54) argues that this professional will take care of providing the role of mediator and must also have knowledge “both in terms of computing, as well as pedagogical and psychological.”

The author clarifies, through his speech, that it is not enough to place a computer genius as a teacher or tutor, if he does not master other fields linked to human gnosiological principles, namely, how human beings learn, why they learn and what mechanisms can be inferred in the activities to achieve more efficient use of the cognitive and mnemonic processes linked to learning.

When this element, the *Teaching Place*, is created and properly presented to the educational segment in question, exhaustive creativity for new fields of knowledge becomes possible in the search for social understandings of educational processes and the appropriation of erudite knowledge. Throughout history, this place has always existed. The great libraries represented it with great mastery; however, there were obstacles of various kinds that limited this space from being visited, allowing it to be explored only by a very privileged few. As it still is today, there is the difficulty of language, since not all works are written in the same language as the learner, making it necessary for the learner to master other languages. These limiting issues also referred to the financial conditions for interested students to travel; to be able to continue studies and research for a relatively long time and the aggravating factor was

the delay in carrying out research that could prove to be fruitless in the case, and should therefore be eliminated.

Cognition involves tangible and intangible elements where the act of the process of knowing involves attention, perception, memory, reasoning, judgment, imagination, thought and language. Although we cannot disagree with Aristotle of Stagira [384-322 BC (2007)] that all knowledge, firstly, passes through the senses, this thought must be expanded and discussed, based on René's interpretation Descartes [1596-1650 (2000)], when he says that all this acquired knowledge needs to be interpreted by someone so that this individual who has absorbed this knowledge can infer its usefulness or uselessness for himself and his desires, wherever it is planted .

However, if left to the individual apprentices' analysis and interpretation, they will give them the most absurd meanings, because they will be starting from absolutely nothing, since the knowledge they possess is their practical experiences, empirical knowledge; therefore, they will not have anything to compare the knowledge they acquire from their studies and subsequent investigations. Because this is how science and scholarship advance; With each discovery made or idea developed, it is necessary to have a space to make and/or produce the confrontation, and this is how we are proposing with the development of the term *Teaching Place* and its consequent conceptualization, taking into account José's inference Armando Valente where he argues that,

Knowledge is what each individual constructs as a product of processing, the interrelationship between interpreting and understanding information. This is the meaning that is attributed and represented in the mind of each individual, based on the information that comes from the environment in which they live. This is something individually constructed, it is impossible to transmit itself - what is transmitted is the information that comes from this knowledge, however, never the knowledge itself (VALENTE, 2005, p. 83).

However, when you have a broad understanding of what was mentioned above, no matter how much the teacher tries to transmit knowledge to students, his work will be doomed to failure if he does not understand that his task is to promote conditions for these individuals to produce its own knowledge based on everything that was created by the scientists who preceded us. This is where Karl Popper's principle of refutation comes into play.¹

¹ Falsifiability or refutability is the property that an assertion, idea, hypothesis or theory can be shown to be false. An important concept in the philosophy of science, which was proposed by the Austrian philosopher Karl Popper in the 1930s, as a solution to the so-called problem of induction. With the principle of falsifiability, Popper established the moment of criticism of a theory as the point at which it is possible to consider it scientific. Theories that do not offer the possibility of being refuted through experience should be considered as myths, not as science.

Just as M. Heidegger (1889-1976) highlights that the essence of technique is technique in movement, by analogy, we have that the essence of knowledge is knowledge in movement, applied to objects, inducing ways of being and of thinking abstractly and this will never be linear, not both from a horizontal and vertical point of view, because it requires something more than production, immersion, discovery, hypothesis, theorization, synthesis, being all of this, to put into motion the knowledge with which and from which you want to build knowledge. And with each advance, there is a greater need for understanding and understanding the processes that involve knowledge as an essential part of scientific production. It is necessary to discover how to innovate without completely destroying everything that is already known as a known fact, that is, what we are looking for are ways of managing the knowledge we have, with the aim of achieving maximum success. in didactic-pedagogical actions. This requires other tools, more dynamic and much more complex in the sense of structuring and destructuring short, medium and long-term objectives, which are aimed at applying and promoting the Teaching Place as a didactic-pedagogical tool that generates erudite knowledge, the starting from what is known, in fact, which does not translate into a condition of ease, because the new processes of knowledge formation will suppress everything that is obsolete without worrying about the birth pain of those who do not adapt to the world and its constant ways of innovating knowledge.

The condition must be clarified that all knowledge must be properly managed, in such a way that it becomes accessible to the greatest number of individuals possible, thus improving their working conditions, studies, teaching, learning and other evolutionary processes, they must have instruments that enable their broad understanding and interpretation in an autonomous and useful way. All knowledge, however simple it may be, and this is a euphemism, because the mere fact that something is treated under the name of knowledge, this, in itself, automatically makes it an element of high complexity, it must be pragmatic, sustainable and capable of provoking revolutions in thought, social life and individual existence.

Therefore, our interest is to produce, based on the consolidation and systematization of the concept of *Teaching Place*, a space for the production, improvement and perfection of ideas that arise from the space-time changes that constitute human existence and its inexhaustible need for expansion. of everything it knows, giving new epistemological meanings to scientific discoveries at each specific moment in the continuous and infinite history of science, neither before nor after.

Saying that a scientific theory must be empirically falsifiable means saying that a scientific theory must offer the possibility of refutation – and, if refuted, they must not be considered. (AT)

The *Teaching Place* is a term that could never even be imagined in another time in human history, because it appears to confer power, substance and sustainability to *ICT Education* and this is a reality of the contemporary moment in the history of humanity, this temporality that receives the epithet of *Era ICT*.

The *Teaching Place* is not just a technical-scientific term; it represents much more, going beyond what a technological tool can be in a didactic-methodological space, and can be understood as a brain through which the collected data will be forwarded and from where the processed analyzes and interpretations will come from. It is the space where all actors involved in the mission of providing education must be, because not only will individuals emerge prepared, but also able to prepare other individuals to receive and produce knowledge through information and communication technologies, since The teacher in this new space of knowledge must be prepared to guide his students on how they will collect information, how to treat this information and how to use the information obtained through empirical and factual investigation, exploring it through the use of methodologies appropriate to each situation. required. This educator will be the guide for individual self-training and other autonomous individuals, in addition to being able to act as a student learning advisor, both stimulating individual work and supporting the investigative-extensive work of small groups brought together by areas of interest.

However, it is necessary to develop intellectuality which, for Santiago (2015), represents a concept that involves the entire set of intellectual and cognitive faculties, through which tangible and intangible impressions, received by the senses, become a concept that involves the set of intellectual faculties, that is, they are converted into useful knowledge, capable of being applied to solve problems. These developed faculties qualify and enable the individual to perceive, interpret, analyze, apprehend, understand and penetrate the investigative processes with more acuteness and insight, all of this guaranteed by the symbolic mediation that implies the internalization of signs, the use of instruments and the transformation of tool techniques. Therefore, intellectuality goes much further than what was previously exposed, including in its psychodynamic context the fine capacity for abstraction, not clinging to situations of success and failure as if it were a way of planning actions for the near or distant future.

Complementing the previously exposed idea, Jerome Brunner infers that intellectual development,

It is characterized by an increasing independence in the response in relation to the immediate nature of the stimulus. [...] characterizing a growing capacity to deal with alternatives simultaneously and, to attend to several sequences at the same time and to distribute time and attention, in an appropriate way to all these multiple demands (BRUNER, 1975, pp. 17-18).

Intellectual capacity is always ready to develop new structures of thought, in order to expand the framework of possibilities and instruments capable of promoting technical-scientific advances. Once applied to elements of nature and problem situations posed by society to scientists, it produces what is recommended as intelligence, which can be understood as an abstract way of solving the existential enigmas inherent to human life, which are followed by others that are solved. of greater complexity, in an eternal *continuum* . Hence the need to look for elements in history that can provide foundations for what is studied in the present.

In this sense, Jaspers (1991, p. 78) states that “the intellect, as scientific knowledge, is dependent on empirical intuition”¹⁴, that is, the formation of intellectuality takes place in the field of knowing how to act to the extent of understanding and understanding of what occurs around the physical space, in which the individual is inserted, as a researcher and/or as a worker, which already indicates that innovations are not strictly dependent on academic titles, but rather, on the ability to carry out competent and skillful readings of man's living spaces with the infinite possibilities that his intellect can discover and create, consciously or not.

It is worth saying that understanding the binomial *education and technology* means being clear that there is no point in having the latest generation of certain technological devices at hand, but yes, it is important to have the education professional as the main actor in the teaching-learning process. Because of all this, he must be able to assume a problematizing, mediating stance, possess an inventive character, have the will and capacity to be able to transform scientific, historical and cultural knowledge produced by humanity through dialectical means, in a reciprocal and simultaneous manner, linking theory to practice and vice versa.

Mcluhan states that,

With technology, Western man acquired the power to act without reaction. We have acquired the art of carrying out the most dangerous social operations with the most complete exemption. Our exemption was an attitude of non-participation. However, in the age of electricity, when our central nervous system is technically designed to involve us in all of humanity, incorporating it into us, we have to involve ourselves, deeply, in each of our actions (MCLUHAN, 1996, p 18).

Therefore, seeking knowledge through these instrumental mediations, materialized in technologies requires a form of collective work in the search for the unity-totality of knowledge to do what is didactic-pedagogical. Contrary to what happens in capitalist industrial production, where technique is only at the service of capital, technologies in pedagogical work must be at the service of exploratory non-competitiveness, but of solidarity work, of an interdisciplinary collective practice with social quality, from the perspective of the transformation of the individuals involved and of society as a whole, understanding that “[...] the intended pedagogical changes presuppose moving from a traditional school to a school in which learning is the result of a very well balanced combination of instruction and construction knowledge, whether or not using ICT” (VALENTE, 2005, p. 94).

For such a didactic-pedagogical situation to be achieved, the individual must understand their function as a social being immersed in a society that places dispute and triumph over others as a source of appreciation and normalization of individual and social conduct. Therefore, this individual must know himself in immense depth so that he can analyze and interpret with the utmost impartiality the waste that may occur during his actions. However, in addition to this, he must be attentive to his role as a knowledge technician, so that he can develop his work no longer governed by pure theory nor by the belief that his practical experience is sufficient to carry out work efficiently and effectively. . Therefore, it must seek to develop a dialectic of knowledge uniting historical knowledge and everyday practical actions, developing an equitable pedagogical praxis based on broad and profound scientific characteristics based on Valente's inference, in which he argues that,

Today's society is becoming very complex and participation in this society will require people with critical, creative, reflective abilities and capable of thinking, learning to learn, working in groups and knowing themselves as an individual. Therefore, it is up to education to form these individuals, however, it can no longer be based solely on the instruction that the teacher transmits to the student, but rather on the development of projects that the learner elaborates and that serves as a background for the construction of different concepts, including the process that the student uses to learn and, in this way, continue learning throughout life (VALENTE, 2005, pp. 94-95).

The term praxis is a very broad concept because it is inserted in an environment that involves practice and theory, representing not an isolated action, but rather a joint one, which produces a relationship of reciprocity and simultaneity between theory and practice. What is really most interesting is that it only happens within the scope of empirical work, which gives it a broadly scientific and reliable character.

A master and/or teacher who can say that he performs praxis during his teaching work is someone who has a broad command of theoretical and empirical knowledge about the content he teaches, as well as the applicability of the same in relation to the directions that direct the activities of the teacher. teaching-learning. And this should be the profile of the teacher who works and who intends to continue working in teaching. A new pedagogical profile, a new didactic stance, in which *the Teaching Position is consolidated* and from there, considering that

Without these changes, the school tends to become a black hole in the lives of individuals, which consumes a significant amount of time in their lives as it fails to prepare citizens capable of acting in the knowledge society. All of this causes an agenda to be determined, which denies and mutilates the learning predisposition that individuals have that does not integrate the use of ICT, which becomes counterproductive. However, if it persists in this direction and continues to prepare obsolete professionals, they will become absolutely necessary in this new scenario of countless learning opportunities that are unfolding (VALENTE, 2005, p. 95).

Therefore, the master and/or teacher of this new century must know how to guide students on how to seek the information they want, and how to treat and use this information appropriately. This care in seeking, beforehand, all the symbolic and motivational apparatus that drives the student's desire for knowledge is necessary and essential, because,

Intelligence, left to itself in a prudent, patient and reflective spirit, especially when it is not inhibited by received doctrines, also tries to take another path, which is the correct one; but with little success, as the spirit without rules or support is very unequal and completely incapable of overcoming the darkness of objects (BACON, 2000, p. 36).

The philosopher states that the human will needs to be oriented towards useful ends that are in coordination with a social search for the solution of problems that provoke and/or awaken endogenous and exogenous conflicts. The human mind needs explanations for everything that happens, it does not find anything within its reach, it imports it from anywhere else or when it is more capable, it creates one that is capable of satisfying its curious spirit. For all this, care must be taken to protect pedagogical and scientific praxis through serious, experimental, exploratory work, thus ensuring that they change, invest and intersect throughout the teacher's work. This is what characterizes the teaching position.

In the teaching position, the teacher does not lose his space as an actor and protagonist of the teaching-learning process, however, he now assumes it with the difference and the pedagogical, didactic and methodological evaluation in which the students' academic praxis is involved, in an attempt to expand understanding regarding the knowledge acquired through empirical experience, which awakens you to reflective practice.

All this happens because the authors consider that a good pedagogical action carried out with due technical competence must be compiled and recorded for future consultation by other actors in practice or in academic-scientific research processes. Likewise, a well-developed idea based on highly scientific principles must be exposed and launched in the daily exercise of teaching and student action. When this creation of practice based on dialectics involves education actors (teachers and students), broad, critical and reflective thinking emerges, capable of carrying out complex analyzes of the present and past reality and projecting a short, medium and long term future in this way. , taking into account that this is a product of the experience of facts, considering that, “there is no conception in the human intellect that has not previously been received, totally or in part, by the sense organs” (HOBBS, 1974, p. 4) .

So, when choosing *the teaching position* as a space for teaching and student training par excellence, it is based on the principle of an integral formation of the human being, integrated with their physical and psychological environment, for this reason there is a constant search for the discipline of their students. cerebral, linguistic, mnemonic senses and the organization of the capacity for literary apprehension and expression.

When we proposed how to define a concept that could give epistemological substance to the term *teaching place* , the reasons that led us to this decision were the fact that all undefined food becomes the object of outdated deductions, loose formulations, analyzes and unfounded interpretations in the same way that happened with the elephant that was analyzed by seven blind wise men in a city in India in which each of the wise men, all blind, each gave their opinion about the animal that was present through the only means of empirical experiments taking as a point of analysis, deduction and interpretation of the part of the animal that chance hit it. This can also be illustrated, through a quote, *below, from* F. Bacon (2000, p. 127), who says, “the spirit begins by establishing such a property or Law (which it always does when it feels abandoned), he would find chimeras, extravagances, principles that rest on ill-defined notions, laws that every day would have to be reformed.”

Therefore, when giving a definition, it is already clear which path can be followed by the actors: whether they chose the path of absorption of the idea and its subsequent complementation and practical application or the path of contradiction and its consequent refutation, in However, they will have to reflect on the subject and the reflections that arise may “produce questions and problems” (VALENTE, 2005, p. 85) for which there may not be immediate answers and will still be contributing to scientific advances, inferring that the engine of the sciences is continuous investigation.

Therefore, the systematization of a concept has the direct objective of avoiding inhospitable digressions, empty of epistemological meaning, which in the end translates into scientific stupidity, which takes no one anywhere. When the actors reach *the position of teacher*, they all work to expand systematic scientific knowledge, and not to satisfy personal pride and vanity.

However, the more transparent the concept is, the greater the possibilities of understanding the object and the better the possibilities of handling the tools related to it . All of this expands the conditions for dialogue and applicability to the teaching-learning processes of techniques that make use of ICT, as a categorical procedure especially in relation to teacher training for this new reality.

CONCLUSION

Through this essay, we intended to conceptualize, epistemologically, the term *the place of the teacher* in which the function of the teacher's work is explained in the face of the new pedagogical science that consists of promoting the development of a scientific attitude of the student towards science itself and life. as processes of didactic advances.

What we sought was to increase awareness that the human mind is not prepared and must be oriented in different directions, according to the demands that society imposes in certain historical moments as elements of balance of the antagonistic forces that challenge intelligence.

As social processes become more complex, the greater the challenges that will be posed to those who dedicate themselves to erudite sciences with the aim of these individuals transforming these problems into active methodologies capable of leading humanity to evolve. to a broader stage of thinking and facing the difficulties posed by nature.

The ICT ERA brought confirmation of the words of the pre-Socratic philosopher Heraclitus (535-475 BC) and the German philosopher Friedrich Nietzsche (1854-1900) that the only permanent thing was impermanence. This unique condition that the 21st century has brought, as an objective reality, that nothing remains as it is, except by the individual will and paradoxically, can, through it, be transmuted, makes the individual position himself to think and question his place in space [if it has one]. At the same time, he feels insecure, because he is no longer the master of time and things; everything escapes his hands as quickly as it arrives.

When presenting a concept for the *Teaching Place* , we seek to make it very clear that this is a very broad construction that does not close in on itself nor can it be understood outside

the socio-temporal context of each specific community, this fact leads to the very particular needs of understanding of the objects that are and will be under observation and scientific studies, also understanding that it is not enough to have a vast technical or pedagogical culture, you need to know how to transform them into useful knowledge for yourself and others, consolidating them through learning autonomously and in coexistence and confrontation with different modalities of ways of thinking, acting and exposing the intermittences and possibilities of educational processes. It is not about adapting to the 21st Century or the ICT ERA, it is necessary to adapt to this new paradigm that is presented to those who are in direct or indirect contact with what is done in the didactic-pedagogical construction; This new paradigm of education is *the Teaching Place*.

The Teaching Place bursts into the academic world, tearing down the existing boundaries between right and wrong, true and false, in order to create a concept that only constant, systematic, pragmatic study can guarantee any epistemological achievement, thus making it clear that the only permanent thing has become the frightening impermanence of different events and the teacher must be attentive and prepared to act on and in these situations of organized didactic conflicts, but over which he does not have full control, because they are beyond of your capabilities and abilities to predict them. The master is for his student what reason is for madness, the worlds overlap, knowledge and the search for knowledge become part of the desire to find a truth that helps in the psychological understanding of the objects studied.

In this didactic situation, there is no intention of re-creating and/or reconstructing the knowledge already produced and/or acquired by students; the idea is that these new elements will be added to the epistemological-cognitive structure that already exists and that, in its own way, allowed human thought to advance to the point of creating a Teaching Place, in which the interaction procedures between the most several fields linked to the principles of Pedagogy and Didactics were expanded until reaching a possible limit that imposes new needs for breaking paradigms, raising increasingly sophisticated demands on scholars at all levels. When we say here that we do not propose to reconstruct any knowledge, it is because, it is based on the assumption that an epistemological relationship that calls itself dialectical and that is done as such, must take into account the highest regard that the knowledge and knowledge that underlies a new theory or a new methodology is not in harmony with what will emerge again, considering that this new way of thinking and doing will arouse conflicts and it will be from these clashes that the appropriate answers and conclusions that will enable the construction of new paths for science are expected. . However, it cannot be denied that it is the concepts, knowledge and

precepts that everyone loves to classify as traditional and archaic that founded and made possible the technical-scientific advances that we now all enjoy and that allow and empower us to think about new processes of advancement, more dynamic, more efficient and with potential for effectiveness.

This article concludes with the conviction that didactic-methodological processes involving teaching actions that use ICTs need to have the *teaching position* as the guiding axis of pedagogical praxis, especially considering that the intention at this historical moment is the development of an open and prone mentality to advances brought about by the autonomous desires of students, who are committed to producing new ways of doing erudite science. With all this, epistemological advances of great value for teaching practice and learning are expected, bringing the cognitive and intellectual aspects of scientific knowledge increasingly closer together.

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